

The Mental Healthcare Act, 2017 and Law Enforcement: A Comparative Awareness Study across Two Districts in Himachal Pradesh

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ABSTRACT

Mental Healthcare Act, 2017 is landmark legislation passed by the parliament of India and received assent of President of India on 7th April 2017. The provisions of the act was incorporated as a result of ratification of United Nation declaration of rights of persons with disabilities in 2007 and subsequent amendments in the old legislation i.e. Mental Healthcare Act, 1987. The present paper empirically assesses the level of awareness among police personnel towards discharge of duties with respect to the provisions under MHCA-2017. Further, the study tries to find out the challenges in enforcement of mental health law. A simple random sampling method is adopted to collect data through schedule interview in police stations and thanas located in municipal corporation/council (MC) of two districts of Himachal Pradesh viz. Shimla and Kangra. The total samples n=40 taken from the municipal corporation/council of two districts viz. MC-Shimla and MC-Kangra, the data is analyzed using Chi-Square statistical method in Microsoft excel as well as qualitative data analysis method is adopted. The results from the data revealed that the police personnel from MC-Shimla are proportionately 45% more aware about provisions under MHCA-2017, as compare to the police personnel from MC-Kangra. Further, it is found that there is no co-ordination among the stakeholders viz. state mental healthcare authority, mental healthcare review board, mental health establishments and the police departments.

Keywords: *mental healthcare act 2017, police administration, police personnel, enforcement, mental health law.*

INTRODUCTION

Mental health refers to a state of well-being in which an individual realizes their abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, work productively, and contribute to their community (World Health Organization [WHO], 2022). In India, mental health has long been a neglected issue due to stigma, lack of awareness,

and inadequate healthcare infrastructure. However, recent legislative developments have sought to address these challenges. The Mental Healthcare Act (MHCA), 2017, is a landmark legislation that replaced the outdated Mental Health Act of 1987, aligning India's mental health framework with international standards such as the

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United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCPRD) (Mental Healthcare Act, 2017). The MHCA emphasizes the rights of individuals with mental illness, including the right to access treatment, protection from discrimination, and the right to live with dignity. It also decriminalizes suicide, recognizing it as a manifestation of severe mental distress (Sahu et al., 2020). Despite these advancements, implementation remains a challenge due to insufficient funding, a shortage of mental health professionals, and persistent societal stigma (Patel et al., 2018). The National Mental Health Programme (NMHP) and the District Mental Health Programme (DMHP) aim to integrate mental health services into primary healthcare, but their reach remains limited in rural areas (Ministry of Health and Family Welfare [MoHFW], 2019). Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated mental health issues, highlighting the urgent need for robust mental health policies and infrastructure (Chatterjee et al., 2020). While India has made significant strides in mental health legislation, sustained efforts are required to ensure equitable access to care, reduce stigma, and improve awareness. The MHCA, 2017, represents a progressive step, but its success depends on effective enforcement, adequate resources, and societal acceptance of mental health as a critical component of overall well-being

LITERATURE REVIEW

The **Mental Healthcare Act (MHCA) 2017** is landmark legislation in India that aims to protect the rights of individuals with mental illness and ensure access to mental healthcare services (Ministry of Law and

Justice, 2017). One critical aspect of this act is its implications for law enforcement, as police personnel often encounter individuals with mental health conditions in crisis situations (Pathare et al., 2019). However, studies suggest that awareness of mental health laws among police officers remains inadequate, which can hinder effective implementation (Gowda et al., 2018).

In India, police personnel frequently serve as first responders in mental health emergencies, yet their training on mental health legislation is often insufficient (Narayan et al., 2021). Research conducted in other Indian states, such as Karnataka and Maharashtra, indicates that many police officers are unaware of key provisions of the MHCA 2017, including decriminalization of suicide (Section 115) and the right to confidentiality for persons with mental illness (Sagar et al., 2020). Given that police play a crucial role in implementing mental health policies, their lack of awareness can lead to human rights violations and inadequate care (Kumar et al., 2022).

Himachal Pradesh, a predominantly rural state in Northern India, faces unique challenges in mental healthcare delivery due to its hilly terrain and limited mental health infrastructure (Sharma & Gupta, 2021). While studies have examined mental health awareness among healthcare professionals in the region (Thakur et al., 2020), there is a paucity of research focusing on police personnel's knowledge of the MHCA 2017. Given that police in Himachal Pradesh often interact with individuals in mental distress—particularly in remote areas—assessing their awareness of mental health laws is crucial for policy implementation (Verma & Singh, 2022).

Existing literature highlights the need for structured training programs to enhance police officers' understanding of mental health legislation (Math et al., 2019). Successful interventions in states like Tamil Nadu have demonstrated that sensitization workshops can significantly improve police responsiveness to mental health crises (Chandrashekar et al., 2021). However, without baseline data on

awareness levels, designing effective training modules for police in Himachal Pradesh remains challenging. This study aims to bridge this gap by assessing police personnel's awareness of the MHCA 2017 in Himachal Pradesh. Findings will contribute to evidence-based policy recommendations, ensuring better protection of mental health rights in the region.

Table 1.1 Key Provisions of MHCA-2017 with regard to rights of persons with mental illness vis-à-vis role and responsibilities of police

Sr. No	Provision	Description	Role of Police
1	Section 19	Right to access mental healthcare.	Police must ensure individuals with mental illness are not denied access to mental healthcare.
2	Section 20	Right to community living.	Police must protect individuals with mental illness from being forced into homelessness or isolation.
3	Section 21	Right to protection from cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment.	Police must prevent and report any instances of abuse or mistreatment of mentally ill individuals.
4	Section 22	Right to confidentiality.	Police must maintain confidentiality of mental health records during investigations or interactions.
5	Section 23	Right to information about treatment.	Police must ensure individuals are informed about their treatment when involved in mental health cases.
6	Section 25	Advance Directive (right to specify treatment preferences).	Police must respect and uphold advance directives when dealing with mentally ill individuals.
7	Section 89	Duty to report a person with mental illness wandering or in need of support.	Police must assist in taking such individuals to a mental health establishment or safe shelter.

8	Section 100	Admission of a person with mental illness under special circumstances.	Police can assist in transporting individuals to mental health establishments for emergency care.
9	Section 101	Emergency admission and treatment.	Police can help in emergency situations to ensure immediate care for mentally ill individuals.
10	Section 102	Duty of police to protect and assist.	Police must protect individuals with mental illness from harm and assist in accessing care.
11	Section 103	Police powers to enter premises.	Police can enter premises to rescue or assist a person with mental illness if there is a risk of harm.
12	Section 104	Police powers to take individuals into protection.	Police can take individuals into protection if they are found wandering or at risk of harm.
13	Section 105	Police responsibilities in case of suicide attempts.	Police must ensure individuals attempting suicide are treated with dignity and provided mental healthcare.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To assess the level of awareness among police personnel towards discharge of duties with respect to MHCA-2017, in municipal corporation/council of two districts viz. MC-Shimla and MC-Kangra.
- To understand the challenges faced by police personnel in enforcement of mental health law.

HYPOTHESIS

H0: There is no significant difference in level of awareness between police personnel in MC-Shimla and MC-Kangra districts.

H1: Police department is ill equipped to comply with provisions under Mental

Healthcare Act 2017.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To assess the level of awareness among police personnels in municipal corporation/ council of two districts have been selected i.e. MC-Shimla and MC-Kangra of Himachal Pradesh, as these two districts have the major medical college and hospitals with general psychiatry departments established. Along with this, Shimla being the capital of Himachal Pradesh and having state's major mental health hospital and rehabilitation centre situated at Boileuganj, makes the study area more relevant. The data will be collected from primary as well as secondary sources.

The research method is primarily empirical based as the data will be collected through questionnaires and schedules. In order to collect primary data, a simple random sampling method employed to collect the data and total sample of (n=40) police personnels, viz. n=20 from each municipal coporation/council (MC) of Shimla and Kangra is selected from all the police stations and thanas, as mentioned in (Table 1.2 and 1.3), to find out the level of awareness about Mental Healthcare Act 2017. In addition to this, There will also be qualitative data collection which

includes, observation, in-depth interview of the police personnel's, qualitative documents (e.g. newspapers, minutes of meetings, official reports) in order to enhance validity and credibility of the findings. Hence, the nature of data is qualitative and well as quantitative i.e. mixed research methodology. The data processing would involve editing, coding, classification, and tabulation. The data would be analyzed through Chi Square statistical method in Microsoft Excel to get the appropriate results along with qualitative data analysis.

Table 1.2 Shimla Municipal Corporation (SMC) - Police Stations & Wards

Sr. No	Police Station/Thana	Wards Covered	Jurisdiction Area
1	Shimla Police Station (Sadar)	Ward 1-10, Lower Bazaar,	Central Shimla Mall Road
2	Boileauganj Police Station	Ward 11-15, Khalini, Boileauganj	Western Shimla
3	Chhota Shimla Police Station	Ward 16-20, Chhota Shimla, New Shimla	South Shimla
4	Krishnanagar Police Station	Ward 21-25, Krishnanagar, Sanjauli	Northern Shimla
5	Dhalli Police Station	Ward 26-30, Dhalli, Tutu	Upper Shimla
6	Taradevi Police Station	Ward 31-35, Taradevi, Shoghi	Outskirts of Shimla
7	Bharari Police Station	Ward 36-40, Bharari, Tutikandi	Eastern Shimla

Table 1.3 Kangra Municipal Council - Police Stations & Wards

Sr. No	Police Station/Thana	Wards Covered	Jurisdiction Area
1	Kangra Police Station	Ward 1-10, Kangra Town, Old Kangra	Central Kangra
2	Gaggal Police Station	Ward 11-15, Gaggal, Dronagar	Southern Kangra
3	Nagrota Bagwan Police Station	Ward 16-20, Nagrota, Bagwan	Eastern Kangra

Table 1.4 Shimla Municipal Corporation (SMC) - Total Wards: 34

Sr. No	Ward Numbers	Major Areas Covered
1	1-10	Lower Bazaar, Mall Road, Ridge, Lakkar Bazaar
2	11-20	Khalini, Boileauganj, Chhota Shimla, New Shimla
3	21-30	Sanjauli, Krishnanagar, Dhalli, Tutu
4	31-34	Taradevi, Shoghi (Outskirts)

Table 1.5 Kangra Municipal Council (KMC) - Total Wards: 17

Sr. No	Ward Numbers	Major Areas Covered
1	1-10	Kangra Town, Old Kangra, Dronagar
2	11-17	Gaggal, Sidhbari, Nagrota Bagwan

Findings and Hypothesis Testing Through Chi-Square Statistical Method and Qualitative Data Analysis

The Chi-Square test compares observed frequencies with expected frequencies under the null hypothesis, calculating a test statistic (χ^2) by summing the squared differences between observed and expected values, divided by expected values. A higher χ^2 value indicates greater

divergence from the null hypothesis. The result is compared against a critical value from the Chi-Square distribution table based on degrees of freedom and a chosen significance level (e.g., 0.05). If the test statistic exceeds the critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected, suggesting a significant association or deviation from the expected distribution.

Table 1.6 Chi Square Test to determine level of awareness between MC Shimla's and MC Kangra's police perssonel

Sr. No	District	Yes	No	Total	Expected Frequency	P value
1	MC Shimla	15	5	20	10.5	0.007
2	MC Kangra	6	14	20	9.5	
3	Total	21	19	40		

P value= 0.007 which indicates that the observed differences in awareness levels between the two districts viz. Shimla and Kangra is statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level. In other words, the difference in awareness levels between MC Shimla and MC Kangra is not due to random chance, and there is a meaningful

association between the district and awareness. There is a statistically significant difference in awareness levels between the two districts at ($p=0.007$). The police personnels in MC Shimla has higher level of awareness as compare to the police personnels in MC Kangra, and it is illustrated as below using proportional method.

Table 1.7 Proportional Method to calculate by how much proportion MC Shimla's police personnel have higher level of awareness as compare to the police personel's of MC kangra

Sr. No	District	Yes	Total	Proportion of Yes and level of Awareness	Difference in Awareness Level
1	MC Shimla	15	20	75%	45%
2	MC Kangra	6	20	30%	
3	Total	21	40		

MC Shimla has significantly higher level of awareness (75%) compared to MC Kangra (30%). The difference in awareness levels is 45 percentage points. In other words, MC Shimla has 45% more awareness than MC Kangra among the police personnels.

- Hence, null hypothesis rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted.

Other underlying factors that, why police personnel in MC-Shimla are more aware

as compare to the police personnel in MC-Kangra, as police personnel in MC-Shimla deal with more number of cases of mentally ill patients, which motivates them to study about the provisions of MHCA-2017 in order to understand and discharge of their duties. Further, NGOs, representatives of local bodies and common citizens play important role in rescuing mentally ill patients and

sensitization towards mental health cases. Interpretation of qualitative data reveals that there is absence of trainings and workshops pertaining to MHCA-2017 for skill enhancement and capacity building of police personnel. As there is no coordination among stakeholders viz. State mental healthcare authority, mental healthcare review board, mental healthcare establishments and police departments to promote sensitization and awareness. In addition to this, there is no special unit established in the police stations/thanas specifically dedicated to deal with persons with mental illness, which hinders the discharge of duty effectively. Further, there is a shortage of manpower in police department due to that police personnel have to face extra burden while handling mentally ill patients. There is no specialized training and equipments provided to deal with the persons with severe mental illness.

- *Hence, the second hypothesis is proved to be true.*

SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

Based on the research study and interpretation of the primary as well as secondary data, the following suggestions and conclusions can be made to the policymakers.

1. There is a need of coordination among the administrative and regulatory agencies viz. state mental healthcare authority, mental healthcare review board, mental healthcare establishments and police departments. A proper coordination can yield effective implementation of the provisions under MHCA-2017.
2. The research study revealed that few of the mental healthcare establishments unaware about the amendments in MHCA-1987, due to which police personnel are facing issues in terms of coordination and get support from the staff to comply with the provisions of MCHA-2017. Therefore, state mental healthcare authority as well as government should play a pivotal role to disseminate awareness about MHCA-2017 among various stakeholders.
3. Mental healthcare review board is more or less defunct in the state. There is no trace of its functioning with regards to ensure accountability and responsibility of mental healthcare establishment's vis-à-vis to comply with the MHCA-2017. Hence, mental healthcare review board should actively discharge its duty with respect to mental healthcare establishments.
4. The seminars and workshops related with MHCA-2017 should be organized in regular interval in police departments to enhance capacity building of police personnel.
5. Special unit/cell needs to be established in police departments, specifically dedicated to deal with mentally ill patients. Further, state mental healthcare authority and mental healthcare professionals should give specialized training and equipments to the police personnel to effectively deal with persons with severe mental illness.
6. The scope of TELEMANS APP (a centre government scheme to deal with mental health cases) should

expand in terms of infrastructure and outreach.

7. The sensitization of police personnel towards mentally ill patients have to enhance and government should strive towards reducing stigma associated with mental illness among people in the society.

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